

Enrichment of Copper and Zinc with Activated Carbon and Determination by Atomic Absorption Spectrometry

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MOST of the toxic metals in sea water and fresh water¹ are found at concentrations far below the detection limits of the commonly used analytical methods². Hence, it is necessary to incorporate an additional step of sample pretreatment prior to analysis. This improves both the sensitivity and accuracy of the determination.

Sigworth and Smith³ have reviewed varied applications of separating trace metals and inorganic compounds from aqueous solutions using activated carbon. Jackwerth *et al.*⁴ used different complexing agents for trace metals before adsorption by activated carbon and their subsequent determination

to give the maximum absorbance of 0.200. Instrumental parameters for Cu are lamp current 30 mA, λ 324.8 nm, slit 0.7 nm and the corresponding values for Zn are 15 mA, 213.8 nm, 0.2 nm; flame gas air-acetylene.

Stock solutions of Cu and Zn (1000 mg dm⁻³) were prepared by dissolving the metals in nitric acid and diluted with deionised double-distilled water, and working standards prepared by diluting the stock solutions. Activated carbon (SD's) was purified by treating it with HCl, then washed with double-distilled water and dried at 110°. Potassium butyl xanthate was synthesised and purified⁵, and its solution (0.5% w/v) was prepared in double-distilled water. Water samples collected from different locations were acidified with nitric acid, filtered and preconcentrated.

Determination of copper and zinc: To water sample (100 ml), metal solution (1 ml, containing 20 μ g Cu and 20 μ g Zn) was added and pH adjusted to 10 \pm 0.01. To it, a 0.5% potassium butyl xanthate (6 ml) was added and the solution was stirred with activated carbon (100 mg) for 20 min. The carbon

TABLE I - DETERMINATION OF Cu AND Zn IN WATER SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Metal taken μ g/500 ml		Metal found* μ g/500 ml		Standard deviation	
	Cu	Zn	Cu	Zn	Cu	Zn
1.	10	10	9.82	9.85	0.10	0.10
2.	50	50	46.72	46.90	0.04	0.05
3.	100	100	98.10	98.20	0.08	0.04
	Well water samples :		μ g dm ⁻³	μ g dm ⁻³		
4.	Mangapuram		5.10	74.00	0.04	0.03
5.	Narsingapuram		6.32	168.50	0.04	0.02
6.	Mittapalem		9.26	180.05	0.10	0.10
7.	Chandragiri		13.47	75.60	0.07	0.07
8.	Agarala		8.42	82.00	0.09	0.08
9.	Ithepalli		11.05	175.10	0.03	0.04

*Average of 3 determinations.

by AAS. Activated carbon in the presence of ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate has been used for the separation and determination of metals in water samples⁶. Adsorption of microgram amounts of twenty metal species on activated carbon from aqueous solutions has also been investigated⁶. Determination of traces of Cu, Cd, Pb and Co in pond, river and marine sediments by AAS based on complexation of metals with xanthate followed by their preconcentration on activated carbon has been attempted⁷. The present work deals with the determination of Cu and Zn in water by AAS.

Experimental

Assay of Cu and Zn was done by on a Perkin-Elmer 2380 flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer. All reagents were of analytical grade. The instrument was calibrated by aspirating 1 ppm zinc standard; Nebuliser and fuel-oxidant ratio adjusted

was then filtered off; dried, treated with hot nitric acid (1 ml) which ensured quantitative desorption of metals and finally evaporated to dryness. The metal was then leached in dilute nitric acid (10 ml) and analysed.

Results and Discussion

Study of the retention of copper and zinc by activated carbon showed that these could be quantitatively recovered only in presence of potassium butyl xanthate. Recovery of copper and zinc was maximum at pH 10 \pm 0.01. The recovery of copper and zinc remained same beyond 10 min. The experiment was also carried out by passing the metal ion solution with potassium butyl xanthate through filter paper coated with activated carbon. Stirring of solutions with activated carbon was necessary for satisfactory recovery from 1.32 \times 10⁻³ M xanthate concentration. Optimum concentration

ranges for Zn and Cu were 10–500 and 10–400 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$, respectively, amount of activated carbon, ~ 100 mg sample volume, 50–500 ml.

The proposed method was applied for the analysis of spiked water samples. Trace metals like Co, Ni, Cd, Fe, Pb, As and Hg did not interfere in the determination of copper and zinc (Table 1). The method was also employed for the analysis of field water samples (Table 1). The metal concentrations were enriched by a factor of 10 and the results were compared with ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate extraction method⁹. The results obtained by the two methods were found to agree well.

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